

PRESCHOOL EDUCATION - PROBLEMS AND THEIR SOLUTIONS

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Annotation: The article analyzed problems in preschool education organizations and their solutions.

Key words: preschool educational organizations, children, pedagogy, kindergarten, teaching, upbringing, continuity.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most urgent problems of the modern educational process is the problem of continuity. The issue of implementation of continuity is considered every year in a new way, in the process of introducing new methods and methods of teaching. Modern pedagogy requires unique innovations in teaching, educating and developing each student, and often traditional methods overlap with non-traditional methods.

State requirements for preschool education and state educational standards for elementary education are important steps in the kindergarten and school continuum.

Today, changes are taking place in the education system. They are related to the socio-economic processes taking place in our society. It is also related to the constantly growing flow of information, changing living conditions and the emergence of new requirements for people. We know that the most difficult thing in life is to be fulfilled and look forward to the future with confidence. Therefore, the main condition of human success is, first of all, his psychological qualities, the

ability to communicate and receive information. This means that the main task of the school today is to teach the child to learn.

One of the conditions for continuous education is the continuity of all stages of the educational process.

Experience in the organization of the catering system: It is well known that there were certain problems in the catering system of MTT. Not all food products reached the desired destination. Also, the head of the MTT and the pedagogical staff were distracted from their main work, that is, they had to deal with the organization of the feeding system along with the education of children. That is why special attention is being paid to the transformation of the kindergarten into a pre-school education system.

"That's why we decided to try outsourcing, an alternative to organizing catering. Why was it started as an experiment? After a certain period of time, we will analyze and come to a conclusion about which way is better. Parents' opinions are taken into account, of course."

Staffing and Retraining: Staffing is everything. MTV has had this problem since the early days. Today, the number of MTT is increasing, including non-state pre-school educational institutions. In January, their number was more than 200, and by now this figure is about 600. The numbers are increasing day by day as private MTTs and Public-Private Partnership MTTs are opening. Naturally, the demand for personnel is also high.

"If there are no personnel, there is no need to talk about the quality of preschool education. We have developed the issue of personnel retraining. There are too many pedagogues who do not have a specialty in preschool education. Today, there are jobs for pedagogues in academic lyceums and colleges decreased, they are people who have pedagogical experience, but do not have knowledge of basic preschool education. For such people, 4-month retraining

courses were opened at pedagogical universities. To date, more than 9,400 pedagogues have completed them and were included in the MTV system. In addition, we have developed a new flexible model, that is, 6-month courses have been organized for people without pedagogical education, their number is around 1,500," said the minister of preschool education.

In addition, one should not forget about the new Puchon University in Tashkent. 540 listeners have passed the tests so far. They will become pedagogues of the new generation, these pedagogues will be trained in music education, sports education and other areas and become specialists in all aspects.

2.5 million children between the ages of 3 and 7 are included in the system of the Ministry of Preschool Education. The number of MTTs in the republic is 6154. 5586 of them are state-owned, 568 are non-state educational institutions. As of today, 859,141 children are enrolled in pre-school education, which is 34% of the total. In total, more than 1 million 600 children are not covered by preschool education.

"We were founded on September 30, 2017, when MTTs were handed over to us, their number was 4,891. Currently, 5,586 MTTs are operating. The question may arise: "Where did so many MTTs appear?" we conducted an inventory process. This was noted for the first time in Uzbekistan by a completely foreign organization - an independent consulting company. During the registration, we found out that in addition to our state kindergartens, there are branches that are not controlled by anyone. Therefore, out of 800 such branches, 600 are independent Converted to MTT".

By 2030, it is aimed to cover 85 percent of children in the republic's MTTs.

New models: The goal of the Ministry of Preschool Education is to include all children in an equal and high-quality preschool education system. There are remote rural areas in Uzbekistan, where there are no kindergartens, so it is not

possible to get pre-school education. In order to ensure coverage, MTV has developed a decision on the establishment of an alternative form of training - family MTTs. In addition, women with higher education, who cannot work for certain reasons, have the opportunity to hire workers in their own homes. "women with secondary and special education can also work in family MTT. We will introduce them to the staff and they will be provided with a salary. The ministry will fully undertake the furniture and methodological support". and another model that will be developed in the future - with the help of the Islamic Development Bank, one room will be equipped with pre-school education for children. akam will be given and he will be followed up accordingly. For now, these numbers are obtained from the State Statistics Committee, the Ministry of Justice and Health. The proposal was included in the draft decision that pre-school education organizations can provide additional services for parents who work late. Of course, additional services are provided for an additional fee. It's no secret that until recently, pedagogues in MTTs had to fill out many types of documents. In time, due to red tape, children were not given enough attention. Because they knew very well that failure to meet the demands of the management on time would not lead to good. Many good personnel have given up their favorite professions because of this red tape. And finally, on July 15, 2018, a decision was made to reduce paperwork in MTTs. According to him, previously pedagogues kept 9 types of documents, now their number has been reduced to 4. We hope that all the implemented reforms will be reflected in practice, and our children will be provided with quality pre-school education, and pedagogues will be provided with decent wages and benefits. So that every child does not shed tears because he does not want to go to kindergarten, and good teachers do not give up their profession!

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